

Building Roadmaps to Industrial
Decarbonisation and Green Economy
through EU-China Cooperation

D5.1 – Review of current EU and Chinese modeling gaps and potentials for improvement

WP5 – Integrated Model Development to assess
decarbonisation pathways

<https://www.eu-china-bridge.eu>

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Responsible author	Nicklas Forsell	Email	forsell@iiasa.ac.at	
	IIASA	Phone	+43 676 838 07334	
Contributors	Nicklas Forsell, Fanqi Jia, Lena Höglund [IIASA] Panagiotis Fragkos, Maria Kannavou, Maro Baka, Zoi Vrontisi [E3M] Ershi Hua, Minpeng Chen [RUC], Zhao Xu [SDU]			
Reviewer(s)	Andre Depperman [IIASA]			
Edited and submitted by	Chun Xia [WI]			
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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the Description of the Action (DoA)

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This report will serve as a basis for the EU-China modelling workshop that will take place in October 2024, Weihai, China. During that workshop, the models will be presented not only to consortium members but also to students and colleagues at the Shandong University. Furthermore, the report will serve as a basis for the selection of model improvements to be implemented during the scope of the project.

3. Short summary of results

To achieve the targets of the Paris Agreement, a broad range of socioeconomic sectors must drastically reduce emissions. Models are commonly used to project the development of such sectors and to assess the mitigation potential and outcomes of national and international policies. Given the strong interdependencies between sectors and countries, relying on a single model for designing mitigation pathways would be insufficient. Instead, an integrated modeling framework is recommended, combining models from various disciplines to provide a comprehensive view of the interactions between environmental, economic, and social systems. The EU-China Bridge project focuses on developing and enhancing modeling frameworks to support net-zero emissions pathways in the EU and China. This report provides an overview of the key modelling frameworks being used in Europe and China to support policy makers and how they can be further improved upon to. The report highlights key elements of the model themselves and lays the groundwork for further development of them to improve their accuracy and utility.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

Submission of the report to the project coordinator and presentation of the report on the project homepage.

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Preface

EU-CHINA BRIDGE will support the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society in both Europe and China by jointly advancing knowledge on technology innovations and roadmaps for decarbonising energy intensive industries, co-creating innovative modelling by combining cutting-edge bottom-up and integrated assessment modelling to quantify net-zero sustainable pathways, and developing the most updated and comprehensive emissions data. It will intensively engage relevant stakeholders from both regions, enhancing dialogues, and fostering mutual learning among policymakers, industries, and experts. It will deliver two open-source EU-China joint technology inventories of promising net-zero emission technology options for the iron & steel and chemical industries, two co-implemented demonstrations of promising technologies in China, and co-created scale-up paths and roadmaps of the selected industrial technologies in both regions. It will also develop the most up-to-date, high-resolution, multi-sectoral, national and regional GHG and short-lived climate pollutant emission inventories as well as dynamic monitoring of key emission sources at high spatiotemporal granularity. A state-of-the-art modelling framework will be developed, exploiting and advancing cutting-edge and established modelling tools for EU and China, using the latest emissions data, representing technology and policy options, enabling assessment of socioeconomic impacts, covering multiple economic sectors and regions, and offering high spatial and technology detail. The enhanced models will be used to co-produce net-zero pathways for the EU and China, explicitly assessing co-benefits and trade-offs of climate policies with other societal goals while exploring cooperation policies and governance to drive the global transformation and assessing the distributional and global-level implications of the two regions' decarbonisation. The pathways will be documented in new workspaces in the I²AM PARIS platform.

WI – Wuppertal Institut Fuer Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH	DE	Wuppertal Institut
E3M – E3-Modelling AE	GR	E3 Modelling Energy Economy Environment
IIASA – Internationales Institut fuer angewandte Systemanalyse	AT	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
UoB – The University of Birmingham	UK	UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM
ICCS – Institute of Communication and Computer Systems	GR	ICCS
HOL – HOLISTIC IKE	GR	HOLISTIC
ITE – University of Kassel	DE	UNI KASSEL VERSITÄT
THU-SA – Tsinghua University	CN	
THU-CE – Department of Chemical Engineering, Tsinghua University	CN	清华大学化学工程系 Department of Chemical Engineering, Tsinghua University
THU-DESS – Department of Earth System Science, Tsinghua University	CN	清华大学地球系统科学系 Department of Earth System Science, Tsinghua University
RUC – Renmin University of China	CN	
SDU – Shandong University	CN	山东大学
CHINACOAL – China National Coal Group Corporation	CN	中国中煤能源集团有限公司
BITARIM – Advanced Research Institute of Multidisciplinary Sciences, Beijing Institute of Technology	CN	前沿交叉科学研究院 Advanced Research Institute of Multidisciplinary Sciences
FULONG – Inner Mongolia Fulong Heating Engineering Technology Co., LTD	CN	
BIT-ME – School of Mechanical Engineering, Beijing Institute of Technology	CN	机械与车辆学院

Executive Summary

Models are crucial for providing policy-relevant insights into global environmental change and sustainable development issues by providing a quantitative description of key processes in the human and earth systems and their interactions. Given the multifaceted nature of such processes, relying on a single model for designing and developing mitigation pathways would be insufficient. Instead, an integrated modeling framework is recommended, combining models from various disciplines to provide a comprehensive view of the interactions between environmental, economic, and social systems. This holistic approach ensures that policy development and technological innovations are grounded in evidence.

The project focuses on developing and enhancing modeling frameworks to support net-zero emissions pathways in the EU and China. For the EU27 region, the key models include PRIMES (energy system), GLOBIOM (land use), GAINS (non-CO₂ emissions), and GEM-E3 (macroeconomics), all of which are soft-linked to provide a multidimensional analysis of the net-zero transition. These models cover various sectors and scales, allowing for the design of credible mitigation strategies that consider policy, technological, and behavioral transitions.

For China, models such as AGHG-INV (agriculture) and the GTAP CGE model (socio-economic) assess emissions reduction pathways and the socio-economic impacts of climate neutrality, including labor market transformations and economic growth. Global Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) like PROMETHEUS and GEM-E3 are also employed to analyze the worldwide implications of EU and Chinese decarbonization on trade, commodity markets, and international climate action.

This integrated approach provides valuable insights into the synergies and trade-offs between socioeconomic growth and environmental impacts. The report highlights the WP5 existing models' capabilities, limitations, and potential improvements, offering a powerful tool for shaping effective and sustainable emission mitigation strategies.

It is important to note that this report sets out the first step within the project and outlined potential model improvements that could be implemented during the scope of the project. The final selection of which model improvements to implement will be jointly decided upon and their outcomes presented in report D5.2. The list of potential model improvements as set in this report should as such be considered as a “could do” list and not a “should do” list of model improvements as the decision needs to be taken in joint consideration of the developments with the EU and China, as well as input from the policy makers that the variety of stakeholder that the models are serving.

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1 Introduction

Climate change results from the interaction of numerous factors across different scales and domains. An accurate accounting of GHGs and air pollutants emissions is important to design mitigation pathways. Emissions originate from various sources—industrial processes, transportation, agriculture, land use, and energy production—each of which is influenced by economic policies, technological developments, and social behaviors.

Given this complexity, relying on a single model or discipline to design emission mitigation pathways would be insufficient and potentially biased. An integrated modeling framework is a comprehensive approach that combines various models from different disciplines to simulate and analyze the interactions between environmental, economic, and social systems. These models often incorporate aspects of climate science, economics, energy systems, land use, and policy analysis, enabling a multi-dimensional view of potential emission mitigation strategies. By integrating these diverse perspectives, the framework can provide a more accurate and nuanced understanding of the potential impacts of different policy measures, technological innovations, and behavioral changes. Moreover, integrated modeling frameworks can help to bridge the gap between scientific research and policy development. By translating complex scientific data into practical actions, these frameworks can contribute to designing policies that are both grounded in evidence and aligned with climate change mitigation goals.

Figure 1 The EU-China BRIDGE modeling approach.

This project integrates a diverse set of modeling and data-driven techniques, each offering a unique perspective on sectors, regions, methodologies, and services. Combining these varied approaches allows for a high degree of specificity across spatial, regional, sectoral, and technological dimensions. Moreover, it addresses crucial aspects such as the timing of mitigation strategies, the synergies and trade-offs between socioeconomic growth and environmental impact, spatial distribution and leakage effects, shifts in labor markets, consumer behavior challenges, and adjustments across different sectors.

WP5 is focused on developing an advanced integrated modeling framework to support the development of net-

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zero emission pathways in the EU, China and globally, as illustrated in the modeling frameworks in Figure 1. These models are already deeply embedded within the EU and Chinese policy processes for creating net-zero emission pathways and performing climate policy analysis. The goal of WP5 is to further enhance and expand the EU and Chinese modeling tools used for designing pathways toward carbon neutrality.

Specifically, the models involved in this analytical framework include:

- EU national and sub-national models (PRIMES, GLOBIOM, GAINS, GEM-E3) quantify sector-specific mitigation pathways at both national and sub-national levels. Each of these four key models focuses on a specific sector—energy, land use, macroeconomics, or non-CO₂ emissions—offering high levels of detail. Their integration through soft-linking creates a comprehensive modeling framework, capturing the complex interactions and dimensions necessary for the EU's net-zero transition. The modeling suite aims to develop credible, sector-specific, and economy-wide holistic pathways for achieving net-zero, while also identifying key milestones and the necessary market, technological, policy, and regulatory conditions for 2030 and 2040 to meet long-term net-zero goals.
 - PRIMES model will assess the mitigation options for the EU energy system, exploring energy demand and supply options and their inter-linkages as well as technological, policy and behavioral transition options in major emitting sectors.
 - GLOBIOM/G₄M will be used for assessing land-use-related mitigation opportunities, including the impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services, as well as the impact of lifestyle changes in food consumption.
 - GAINS will assess mitigation potentials of non-CO₂ greenhouse gasses and associated costs and estimate the effects of ambient air quality (fine particles, ground-level ozone, deposition of sulfur and nitrogen) on human health and ecosystems, by displaying estimates of loss in statistical life expectancy under alternative scenarios.
 - GEM-E₃ will be applied for assessing socio-economic challenges and opportunities in the net-zero transition, including the necessary transformations of the labor markets, impacts for economic growth, human welfare and trade, and distributional repercussions across sectors, income classes (e.g. Fragkos et al., 2021) and regions.
- China national and sub-national modeling: The AGHG-INV model focuses on the development of the agricultural sector and will be employed to create deep emissions reduction pathways for China's agricultural industry, with an emphasis on the opportunities and challenges involved in promoting the shift towards healthy and sustainable diets. Additionally, the GTAP computable general equilibrium (CGE) model will be used by Chinese partners to assess the socio-economic challenges and opportunities linked to the transition to climate neutrality. This analysis will cover aspects such as labor market transformation, economic growth, public health, welfare, and the distributional effects across sectors, social groups, and geographic regions.
- EU global IAM models: Global IAM models (PROMETHEUS, GEM-E₃) will be used to quantify the global impacts of EU and China decarbonization on trade, commodity markets, and climate actions in other regions and assess the contributions of the EU and China towards meeting the Paris climate goals. These IAMs are holistic, encompassing all sectors and the interconnections between energy, land systems, the environment, and socio-economics. They maintain consistency with national and EU/China models through both soft- and hard-linkages, as well as data exchange routines. In particular,

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- PROMETHEUS is a global energy system model and projects the development of the global energy system. The model takes as its input the decarbonisation pathways from GLOBIOM and PRIMES for the EU. Furthermore, the modelling framework will include global mitigation potentials of non-CO₂ gases as estimated by GAINS and global mitigation potentials for the land use sector as estimated by GLOBIOM.
- The GEM-E3 model is a global large-scale CGE model and will be applied for assessing the global socio-economic, trade and industrial implications of transition pathways consistently integrating data from energy system pathways (PRIMES for EU, PROMETHEUS for non-EU regions), land-use (GLOBIOM) and non-CO₂ (GAINS) models as in (Fragkos et al., 2018).
- China global IAM model: The GTAP (Global Trade Analysis Project) will be used for analyzing international trade policies, economic integration, and global economic issues. The model will estimate the GHG emissions from the energy and land use sector and assess the dynamics of land use and land cover change, labor migration, and poverty and trade liberalization.

The modeling frameworks will provide a powerful tool for understanding the intricate interactions between environmental, economic, and technological advancements, enabling the development of strategies that are both effective and sustainable. This report presents an overview of the current modeling toolboxes being used to capture sectoral perspectives of net-zero emissions, identifying their current limitations and potential model improvements to contribute to developing emission mitigation pathways in WP6. Within the scope of this specific report, we will focus on the interlinkages between these specific set of models, while in D5.2 will also account for and detail the data exchange and harmonization of assumptions the bottom-up technology specific models from WP3 related to the steel, chemical and industrial waste heat.

2 Overview of existing models

This section provides the brief summaries of the models proposed within this project. Each model description includes an overview of its mathematical approach, dataset utilized, and output result types, highlighting its essential characteristics such as time horizon, geographic scope, and sectoral coverage required for the project. The existing linkages among models involved in each modeling toolbox is present at the end of the section.

2.1 EU consortium modelling toolbox

2.1.1 GEM-E3

GEM-E3 is a large scale multi-sectoral hybrid CGE model designed to evaluate the effects of external shocks on the economy. The model provides a robust framework to capture the complex energy-economy-climate interactions and simulate the impact of climate damages or climate and energy policies on the performance of sectors, sectoral output, prices and bilateral trade, the competitiveness of regions and the welfare of communities. Results have a yearly frequency up to 2030 and 5-year time steps until 2050/2100. The model has a global coverage, with 46 regions, where the G-20 countries, EU27 Member States, and major equipment manufacturing or energy exporting countries are represented individually. All countries are linked through endogenous bilateral trade transactions. The model explicitly represents 68 distinct economic activities, which are interlinked across the production and consumption value chain.

Focus is placed on the representation of the energy system where specialized bottom-up modules of the power generation, buildings and transport sectors have been developed. To this end, the model includes a detailed representation of the power generation system (10 power technologies) and a detailed transport module (private and public transport modes), while different technological options for energy use in buildings and industry are provided. The energy system representation includes an explicit representation of new technologies such as hydrogen, clean fuels, and bioenergy options. The GEM-E3 environment module covers all GHG emissions and a wide range of abatement options, as well as a thoroughly designed carbon market structure (e.g., grandfathering, auctioning, alternative recycling mechanisms). The model has been used extensively by the European Commission, governments and public institutions to assess the macroeconomic, distributional and employment implications of the transition to climate neutrality.

The model is based on advanced applied modelling techniques and has been further extended to allow the representation of semi-endogenous technical progress, endogenous formation of labour skills and human capital and a detailed bottom-up representation of the energy system (in particular transport and power generation), along with non-CO₂ emission abatement options and negative emissions technologies. It moves beyond the standard CGE framework as it is dynamic and features involuntary unemployment in the labour market and alternative macroeconomic closures supported by a detailed representation of the financial sector. The model is established on rigorous microeconomic theory, it is empirically estimated (substitution and trade elasticities) and is able to undertake long term analysis as opposed to econometric models that suffer from the Lucas critique. The model can be used both in a comparative and what if analysis frameworks as represents a closed and consistent accounting of resources.

The model is calibrated to a wide range of datasets comprising of IO tables, financial accounting matrices, institutional transactions, energy balances, GHG inventories, bilateral trade matrices, investment matrices and household budget surveys. All countries in the model are linked through endogenous bilateral trade transactions identifying origin and destination. The substitution elasticities of the model are not derived from the general literature but are estimated according to its dimensions and functional forms using the latest

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available datasets. The model is recursive dynamic through the accumulation of capital via the decision for investments and through the accumulation of knowledge stocks via R&D and human capital development. Model regions are linked through endogenous bilateral trade following the Armington assumption of imperfect substitution across domestic and imported goods. The nested production functions are differentiated by sector and follow a CES structure. For the demand side, the model simulates consumer behaviour and maximizes a Klein-Rubin utility function that results in a Linear Expenditure demand system subject to its disposable income not used for obliged consumption (subsistence minima consumption) and after allowing for the decision on savings. The representative household decides on the allocation of its available for consumption income over different consumption categories (COICOP), distinguishing between durable and non-durable goods. The model has been calibrated to the latest statistics (GTAP 11, IEA, UN, ILO) while Eurostat statistics have been used for the EU.

The key innovations of the model relate to the explicit representation of the financial sector, semi-endogenous dynamics based on R&D induced technical progress and knowledge spillovers, the representation of multiple households, unemployment in the labour market with a representation of five labour skill levels and endogenous formation of labour skills.

The most important results, provided by GEM-E3 are: Full Input-Output tables for each country/region identified in the model, GDP and GDP components, employment by economic activity and by skill and unemployment rates, capital, interest rates and investment by country and sector, private and public consumption, bilateral trade flows, consumption matrices by product and investment matrix by ownership branch, GHG emissions by country, sector and fuel and detailed energy system projections (energy demand by sector and fuel, power generation mix, deployment of transport technologies, energy efficiency improvements).

GEM-E3 enables a thorough understanding and detailed identification of risks and opportunities of the low carbon transition and of the implementation of specific climate and energy policies by capturing:

- Direct impacts on each sector, e.g., how carbon prices and carbon border taxes will affect a sector's costs of production (considering carbon intensity) and thus its production levels (via domestic and international demand)
- Indirect impacts via value chain effects (e.g. changes in prices of intermediate products, of labour and capital inputs), technology costs, consumer preferences, material availability and costs
- Induced effects via economy feedbacks, prices and income implications (e.g. overall drop of demand even for products not directly affected by carbon prices etc.)
- The impacts of financing requirements (capital-intensive process of mitigation) and different financing options
- Impacts on competitiveness by location site
- Impacts on sectoral productivity, household incomes and prices due to climate damages

2.1.2 PRIMES

The **PR**ice-Induced **M**arket **E**quilibrium System (**PRIMES**) model is a large-scale applied energy system model that provides detailed projections of energy demand, supply, prices and investment to the future, covering the entire energy system, all energy demand and supply sectors, including emissions (Figure 2). The distinctive feature of PRIMES is the combination of behavioral modelling (following a micro-economic foundation) with

engineering aspects, covering all energy sectors and markets. The model has a detailed representation of policy instruments related to energy markets and climate, including market drivers, standards, and targets by sector or overall (over the entire system). It handles multiple policy objectives, such as GHG emission reductions, energy efficiency, renewable energy targets, and provides a pan-European simulation of internal markets for electricity and gas.

Figure 2 PRIMES core modelling suite and model overview

PRIMES offers the possibility of handling market distortions, barriers to rational decisions, behaviors, as well as market coordination issues and includes a complete accounting of costs (CAPEX and OPEX) and investment expenditure on infrastructure needs. PRIMES is designed to analyse complex interactions within the energy system in a multiple agent – multiple markets framework.

Decisions by agents are formulated based on a microeconomic foundation (utility maximization, cost minimization and market equilibrium) embedding engineering constraints, behavioural elements and an explicit representation of technologies and vintages and optionally perfect or imperfect foresight for the modelling of investments in all sectors. PRIMES is well-placed to simulate medium and long-term transformations of the energy system (rather than short-term ones) and includes non-linear formulation of potentials by type (resources, sites, acceptability etc.) and technology learning.

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Mathematically PRIMES is described as an Equilibrium Problem with Equilibrium Constraints (EPEC), which allows prices to be explicitly determined. Prices influence demand and demand influences in turn supply. The demand and supply modules are subject to system-wide constraints, which when binding convey non-zero shadow prices (dual values) to the demand and supply modules. Therefore, the PRIMES model has overall a mixed-complementarity mathematical structure.

The full suite comprises the following models:

- **PRIMES-TREMOVE transport model:** includes linkage to synthetic fuels and hydrogen, the latest CO₂ standards including a new categorisation for HDVs, as well as the extension of the ETS.
- **PRIMES BuiMo residential and services model:** high resolution model with representation of the housing and office building stock, embedded in an economic-engineering model of multi-agent choice of building renovation, heating system and equipment/appliances by energy use.
- **PRIMES-Industry model:** very detailed industrial model that includes a high-resolution split of industrial consumption by sector and type of industrial process, the possibility of using hydrogen and synthetic fuels directly, as well as extended possibilities of electrification and the possible emergence of non-fossil hydrocarbon feedstock in the chemicals, process emissions, and carbon usage (CCUS).
- **PRIMES Biomass supply model:** detailed biomass supply model that includes land use constraints, many types of biomass and waste feedstock, sustainability regulation, and endogenous learning and industrial maturity of a large number of potential biomass to biofuels conversion technologies; with linkage with the IIASA models that handle LULUCF and forestry, as well as linkage with the agricultural model CAPRI and alignment of the waste sector with the GAINS model.
- **PRIMES Electricity and Heat/Steam supply and market model:** the modelling includes the hourly unit commitment model - with a pan-European market simulation over the grid constraints and detailed technical operation restrictions - the long-term power system expansion model, the costing and pricing electricity and grid model, the integration of heat supply and industrial steam supply with synchronised hourly operation.
- **PRIMES Gas Supply and Market model:** a stand-alone model representing in detail the gas supply and infrastructure in the Eurasian and Middle-East area and the internal European market of gas within an oligopoly model embedding engineering gas flow modelling.
- **PRIMES new Fuels and storage model** covering Hydrogen, Synthetic fuels, Power-to-X, CO₂ capture from the air and biogenic, CCS/CCU and process-emissions modelling to enhance and perform sectoral integration aiming at simulating a zero-CO₂ system.
- **PRIMES IEM model:** a simulation tool for the internal energy market; it aims to simulate in detail the sequence of operation of the European electricity markets, namely the day-ahead market, the intraday and balancing markets and finally the reserve and ancillary services market or procurement.

2.1.3 PROMETHEUS

PROMETHEUS is a global multi-regional energy system model and covers in detail the complex interactions between energy demand, energy supply, and energy prices at the regional and global level (Figure 3). PROMETHEUS is a comprehensive energy demand and supply simulation model aiming at addressing energy system analysis, energy price projections, power generation planning and climate change mitigation policies. Fossil and renewable energy resources and reserves are represented in detail by region. Furthermore, the

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model handles the interactions between climate policies, energy restructuring and energy price formation (global and regional). Interactions of transformational pathways are assessed across sectors and regions and the model can quantify linkages between global and regional energy and carbon markets. PROMETHEUS modular structure ensures proper module interlinkages and facilitates expansion towards Integrated Assessment Modelling (e.g., links with land-use, climate impacts, biodiversity) and allows the possibility of Monte Carlo runs.

Figure 3. PROMETHEUS model architecture

PROMETHEUS has been expanded and is employed for Integrated Assessment of low-emission strategies in various research projects, while contributing scenarios for the IPCC AR6 (Figure 4). It is a useful tool to support impact analysis and develop climate change mitigation pathways at the national, regional and global scale and can be further used to assess the interactions of transformational pathways across sectors and regions.

PROMETHEUS is designed to provide medium and long term energy system projections and system restructuring up to 2050 (and will be soon expanded to 2100), both in the demand and the supply sides. The model produces analytical quantitative results in the form of detailed energy balances in the period 2015 to 2050 annually. The model can support impact assessment of specific energy and environment policies and measures, applied at regional and global level, including price signals, such as taxation, subsidies, technology and energy efficiency promoting policies, RES supporting policies, environmental policies and technology standards

The PROMETHEUS model provides detailed projections of energy demand, supply, power generation mix, energy-related carbon emissions, energy prices and investment to the future covering the global energy system. PROMETHEUS is a fully fledged energy demand and supply simulation model aiming at addressing energy system analysis, energy price projections, power generation planning and climate change mitigation policies. PROMETHEUS contains relations and/or exogenous variables for all the main quantities, which are of interest in the context of general energy systems analysis. These include demographic and economic activity indicators, primary and final energy consumption by main fuel, fuel resources and prices, CO₂ emissions, greenhouse gases concentrations and technology dynamics (for power generation, road transport, hydrogen production and industrial and residential end-use technologies).

Figure 4. PROMETHEUS model overview.

PROMETHEUS quantifies CO₂ emissions and incorporates environmentally oriented emission abatement technologies (including renewable energy, electric vehicles, Carbon Capture and Storage, energy efficiency, electrification, green hydrogen, advanced biofuels) and energy and climate policy instruments. The latter include both market based instruments such as cap and trade systems with differential application per region and sector specific policies and measures focusing on specific carbon emitting activities. Key characteristics of the model, that are particularly pertinent for performing the analysis of the implications of alternative climate abatement scenarios, include world supply/demand resolution for determining the prices of internationally traded fuels and technology dynamics mechanisms for simulating spill-over effects for technological improvements (increased uptake of a new technology in one part of the world leads to improvements through learning by experience which eventually benefits the energy systems in other parts of the World). PROMETHEUS is designed to provide medium and long term energy system projections and system restructuring up to 2050 (and 2100), both in the energy demand and the supply sides. The model produces analytical quantitative results in the form of detailed energy balances in the period 2015 to 2050 annually (to be expanded to 2100). The model can support impact assessment of specific energy and environment policies and measures, applied at regional and global level, including price signals, such as taxation, subsidies, technology and energy efficiency promoting policies, RES supporting policies, environmental policies and technology standards.

The PROMETHEUS model is organized in sub-models (modules), each one representing the behaviour of a representative agent, a demander and/or a supplier of energy. Figure 3 presents a simplified summary flow chart of the PROMETHEUS model. The main modules are:

- The demographic and economic activity module, which projects population and activity growth for each region.
- The fossil fuel supply module that includes oil and gas resources, while coal is assumed to have abundant supplies relative to production prospects at least for the projection time horizon
- The biomass supply module, which contains technical and economic potential for biomass per region and their effects on biomass costs.
- The cost-supply curves for renewable energy sources (RES) module.

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- The fuel prices module projecting both international and final consumer prices, with the latter being differentiated for each demand sector. Global fossil fuel prices are determined from the equilibrium of fuel demand and supply at the global level.
- The final energy demand module, projecting energy demand and fuel mix in three main sectors; industry, transport and residential/services/agriculture sector. The following energy forms are considered as options in the final demand sectors: natural gas, oil, coal, biofuels, electricity, steam and hydrogen. The private passenger cars sector is modelled in detail, by distinguishing the following types of passenger cars: internal combustion engine cars (using gasoline, diesel, biofuels or hydrogen as a fuel), conventional and plug-in hybrids, electric cars and fuel-cell cars (using hydrogen or gasoline as a fuel).
- The electricity generation module, identifying 26 power generation technologies and their competition to cover electricity demand for base, medium and peak load.
- The hydrogen production sub-model, identifying 18 hydrogen production options
- The hydrogen storage and delivery module, including 16 different technological options in order to represent in detail the development of hydrogen infrastructure.
- The technology dynamics module, which endogenises technical progress through both learning by research and learning by experience (“learning by doing”) mechanisms.
- The technology diffusion module incorporating network effects accelerating spillovers between regions in cases where technology uptake attains critical levels

PROMETHEUS is a recursive dynamic energy system simulation model. Variables are either calculated directly or are calculated based on the previous years' values, to which are applied the evolution of explanatory variables and other exogenous parameters. The economic decisions regarding the investment and operation of the energy system are based on the current state of knowledge of parameters (costs and performance of technologies, prices, ...) or with a myopic anticipation of future costs and constraints. The model does not use foresight but myopic anticipation. Some foresight can be forced in the electricity production sector. The core operating principle of the PROMETHEUS model is that of market equilibrium. The representative agents in the modules use information on prices and make decisions about the allocation of resources. They represent, for example, regional electricity sectors, regional refining sectors, regional energy demand sectors. Markets are the means by which these representative agents interact with one another. The model solves for a set of market prices so that supplies and demands are balanced in all these markets across the model; in other words, market equilibrium is assumed to take place in each one of these markets (partial equilibrium), and not in the entire economy across all markets (general equilibrium). The solution process is the process of iterating on market prices until this equilibrium is reached. The regional fuel markets are also integrated to form an international (global or regional) market equilibrium for crude oil, natural gas and coal.

2.1.4 GLOBIOM

The **Global Biosphere Management Model** (GLOBIOM¹) is an economic model designed to address various land use related topics (bioenergy and climate policy impacts, deforestation dynamics, climate change adaptation

¹ www.iiasa.ac.at/GLOBIOM

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and mitigation from agriculture, long term agricultural prospect). It is a partial equilibrium model, meaning that the only economic sectors represented in detail are agriculture (including livestock), forestry and bioenergy. In the EU-China Bridge Project, the regional model of GLOBIOM, GLOBIOM-EU, will be used. The main characteristics of GLOBIOM-EU are summarized in Figure 5.

GLOBIOM-EU [2022]	
Model framework	Partial equilibrium, bottom-up, starts from spatially explicit land and technology representation
Sector coverage	Detailed focus on agriculture (including livestock), forestry and bioenergy
Regional coverage	Global (27 EU Member states + 31 regions)
Resolution on production side	Detailed grid-cell level (>10,000 units worldwide)
Time frame	2000-2070 (ten-year time step)
Market data source	EUROSTAT and FAOSTAT
Factor of production explicitly modelled	More detailed on natural resources (land, water)
Land use change mechanisms	Grid-based (aggregated to NUTS2 level for EU). Land conversion possibilities allocated to grid-cells taking into account suitability, protected areas.
Representation of technology	Detailed biophysical model estimates for agriculture and forestry with several management systems. Literature reviews for biofuel processing.
Demand side representation	One representative consumer per region and per good, reacting to the price of this good.
GHG accounting	12 sources of GHG emissions covering crop cultivation, livestock, above and below ground living biomass and soil organic carbon.

Figure 5. Main structural characteristics of GLOBIOM-EU.

As a model specialized in land use-based activities, GLOBIOM benefits from a detailed sectoral coverage, with an explicit representation of production technologies, a geographically explicit allocation of land cover and land use and their related carbon stocks and greenhouse gas emission flows.

Figure 6 presents an overview of the model framework. The supply side of the model is built-up from the bottom (spatially explicit land cover, land use, management systems information) to the top (regional markets). The model is solved recursively dynamic and can provide projections up to 2100. The agricultural and forest productivity is modeled at the level of Simulation Units (SimU), aggregates of 5 x 5 to 30 x 30 minutes of arc pixels belonging to the same country, altitude, slope, and soil class (Skalský et al., 2008). For the EU (except Croatia, Cyprus, and Malta) a more detailed SimU architecture (Balkovic et al., 2009) is used (i.e., basic spatial unit is a 1x1 km pixel, six altitude and seven slope classes, soil classes are characterized by soil texture compositions, depth, and coarse fragment content, NUTS2 regions boundaries plus additional dimensions for land cover category, presence of irrigation equipment, and river catchment reference) (Figure 7). Demand and international trade occur at regional level (58 regions), covering all EU27 member states and 31 regions in the rest of the world. Besides primary products for the different sectors, the model has several final and by-products, for which the processing activities are defined.

Figure 6: Overview of the GLOBIOM model structure.

The model computes market equilibrium for agricultural and forest products by allocating land use among production activities to maximize the sum of producer and consumer surplus, subject to resource, technological, demand and policy constraints. The level of production in a given area is determined by the agricultural or forestry productivity in that area (dependent on suitability and management), by market prices (reflecting the level of demand), and by the conditions and cost associated to conversion of the land, to expansion of the production and, when relevant, to international market access. Trade is modelled following the spatial equilibrium approach (Takayama and Judge, 1971), which means that the trade flows are balanced out between different specific geographical regions. Trade is furthermore based purely on cost competitiveness as goods are assumed to be homogenous. This allows tracing of bilateral trade flows between individual regions.

The model allows for a full account of all agriculture and forestry GHG sources. GLOBIOM accounts from main sources of GHG emissions, including N₂O emissions from fertilizer use, CH₄ from rice cultivation, livestock CH₄ emissions from enteric fermentation, CH₄ and N₂O emissions from manure management, N₂O from manure applied and dropped on pasture, above and below ground biomass CO₂ emissions from biomass following land use or management changes, and CO₂ emissions from soil carbon. The emissions inventories are based on IPCC accounting guidelines. In addition, GLOBIOM endogenously represents three major mitigation mechanisms in the agricultural sector at global scale: i) technological mitigation options, ii) structural changes such as switches in production systems (tillage, fertilizer, water management etc.) or international trade, and iii) feedback on the demand side through consumers' response to price changes (Frank et al., 2018). For the EU, GLOBIOM

covers explicitly agricultural carbon sequestration options (Frank et al., 2015; Frank et al., 2016).

Figure 7. Simulation Unit representation in GLOBIOM-EU. Pixels with the same colour have the same biophysical soil properties.

2.1.5 G₄M

The Global Forest Model (G₄M²) is applied and developed by IIASA (Kindermann et al., 2006; Gusti et al., 2008; Kindermann et al., 2008; Gusti, 2010; Gusti, 2010; Gusti and Kindermann, 2011) and estimates the impact of forestry activities (afforestation, deforestation, residue harvest and forest management) on biomass and carbon stocks. By comparing the net present value of managed forest (difference of wood price and harvesting costs, income by storing carbon in forests) with income by alternative land use on the same place, a decision on afforestation or deforestation is made. The model incorporates empirical forest growth functions for major tree species. G₄M is spatially explicit and runs on a 0.5° x 0.5° resolution. Since the model does not represent either forest markets or other economic sectors, it has to rely on information from other sources – (i.e., GLOBIOM or other databases) – for wood prices, land rents, urban sprawl etc. Similarly, information about natural disturbances comes as input to the model. As outputs, G₄M produces estimates of forest area change, carbon sequestration and emissions in forests, impacts of carbon incentives (e.g., avoided deforestation) and supply of biomass for bioenergy and timber.

The main forest management options considered by G₄M are variation of thinning, harvest intensity and forest residue collection. The harvest intensity is modelled through defining whether forest is used for intensive wood production (further is called managed) or not (further called unmanaged), and for the intensively used forest the harvest is determined by the choice of rotation length. The rotation length can be individually chosen but

² www.iiasa.ac.at/G4M

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the model can estimate optimal rotation lengths to maximize increment, stocking biomass or harvestable biomass.

The model uses projections of wood demand per country estimated by GLOBIOM to calculate total harvest iteratively. G₄M uses 2000-2010 average wood production map by Verkerk et al. (2015) to initialize spatially explicit wood production. In the initial year G₄M selects the minimum amount of intensively used cells necessary for sustainable production of demanded amount of wood on country scale. In consequent years, if total harvest is smaller than wood demand, the model changes grid per grid (starting from the most productive forest) the management to a rotation length that optimizes forest mean annual increment and thus allows for more harvest. The rotation length is changed at maximum by 20 years per time step.

Starting from the calibrated afforestation and deforestation rates based on UNFCCC (2023) submissions, G₄M projects the development of future forest area based on the development of basic drivers received from GLOBIOM, i.e., projections of land prices and wood prices but also input from Member States when relevant. The potential value of forestry activities on a grid cell based on wood prices is compared to the land price and a decision on afforestation or deforestation taken by the model. Future demand for wood influences afforestation rates through the wood price estimated by GLOBIOM. Newly established forests contribute to wood production after reaching a certain maturity, i.e., smaller dimensioned timber from thinning after 10 to 15 years and sawn wood after 30 to 50 years in Central Europe. In the longer run increased wood demand also increases afforestation rates.

To ensure consistency in the total land area balance between GLOBIOM and G₄M, GLOBIOM supplies G₄M with the maximum area that can be afforested which excludes cultivated cropland or grassland necessary for food and feed production (e.g., fallow land, abandoned grassland and cropland, etc.) or areas not suitable. Once G₄M has estimated afforestation areas, these are fed back and implemented GLOBIOM in a final iteration. The forest established on afforested land has the same properties, i.e., growth rates, management rules as the forest already existing in neighboring grid cells. This means that forest growth rates of afforested land are rather moderate compared to dedicated short rotation tree plantations established for energy production. Such plantations established on cropland or grassland have high growth rates and short rotations and are not considered to fall into the definition of forest and hence are covered by GLOBIOM.

The models GLOBIOM and G₄M together cover all UNFCCC land use categories of relevance for CO₂ emissions. Only wetlands and settlements are not endogenously modelled. G₄M covers the forestry sector and delivers emissions/removals from biomass and soil carbon changes from afforestation, deforestation and harvest residues collection activities and emissions/removals from forest management. GLOBIOM supplies emissions/removals from cropland and grassland management.

2.1.6 GAINS

2.1.6.1 Model overview

The Greenhouse gas - Air pollution Interactions and Synergies (GAINS) model³ developed by IIASA, describes the pathways of atmospheric pollution from its anthropogenic origin to the most relevant environmental impacts (Amann et al. 2011, 2020). It brings together information on future economic, energy and agricultural

³ http://gains.iiasa.ac.at/models/gains_models4.html

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development, emission control potentials and costs, atmospheric dispersion and environmental sensitivities towards air pollution. The model addresses threats to human health posed by fine particulates and ground-level ozone, risk of ecosystems damage from acidification, excess nitrogen deposition (eutrophication) and exposure to elevated levels of ozone, as well as short-term and long-term radiative forcing. These impacts are considered in a multi-pollutant context, quantifying the contributions of methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), fluorinated gases (HFCs, PFCs and SF₆), black and organic carbon (BC/OC), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), ammonia (NH₃), non-methane volatile organic compounds (VOC), and primary emissions of fine (PM_{2.5}) and coarse (PM_{2.5}-PM₁₀) particles (Figure 8).

	PM	SO ₂	NO _x	VOC	NH ₃	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O	HFCs PFCs SF ₆
Health impacts: PM	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
O ₃			✓	✓			✓		
Vegetation damage: O ₃			✓	✓			✓		
Acidification		✓	✓		✓				
Eutrophication			✓		✓				
Radiative forcing: - direct						✓	✓	✓	✓
- via aerosols	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
- via OH			✓	✓			✓		

Figure 8. The GAINS multi-pollutant/multi-effect framework.

The GAINS model can explore cost-effective strategies to reduce emissions of air pollutants and greenhouse gases in order to meet specified environmental targets. It also assesses how specific control measures simultaneously influence different pollutants, permitting a combined analysis of air pollution and climate change mitigation strategies, which can reveal important synergies and trade-offs between these policy areas. The optimization mode of the GAINS model balances emission control measures across countries, pollutants and economic sectors such that user-defined target levels on various environmental impacts are met at least costs.

A comprehensive description of the European version of the GAINS model is given in (Amann et al., 2011, 2020), which also illustrates the application of the model for policy analysis. Brief descriptions of the model framework for estimations of non-CO₂ emissions and air pollutants, i.e., those aspects of the model of most relevance to the proposed project, are described in the subsequent sections. Further information and documentation can be accessed and downloaded from: http://gains.iiasa.ac.at/models/gains_resources.html.

Emissions are estimated in the GAINS model by multiplying activity levels with average emission factors for given technology structures applied in a given source sector. Air pollutants concentrations and deposition is estimated using a linear source-receptor matrix approach. The model has a global coverage, generating emission estimates for 182 individual countries/regions, including 27 EU member countries, 32 Chinese provinces, and 23 Indian states. The time resolution is 1990-2050 in five-year steps, with a further extension to 2070 for Europe. The GAINS model covers all source sectors with any significant contribution to anthropogenic emissions to air. For each sector, current technology structures' contributions to emissions are identified, which allow for assessing the potential for future abatement potentials and costs as technology structures change.

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The GAINS database is publicly available and can be accessed from <https://iiasa.ac.at/models-tools-data/gains>.

2.1.6.2 Modelling non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions

The non-CO₂ greenhouse gases (GHGs) represented in the GAINS model include methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons (PFCs), sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆), as well as the short-lived climate forcers black carbon (BC) and organic carbon (OC). The GAINS model has been used on several occasions to estimate current and future emissions of non-CO₂ GHGs in the European Union in support of EU's climate strategy (e.g., Höglund-Isaksson et al., 2012, 2023; EC, 2021). On the global scale, the GAINS model has been used to explore technical mitigation opportunities and costs at the gas and sector level (Höglund-Isaksson, 2012; Höglund-Isaksson et al., 2020; Purohit et al., 2017, 2020, 2022; Winiwarter et al., 2018; Gomez-Sanabria et al., 2022).

GAINS is part of the EUCLIMIT model consortium led by the PRIMES model team. The model consortium has since 2009 been contracted by the European Commission DG-CLIMA to provide analytical scientific inputs to the EU climate policy impact assessments. Within EUCLIMIT, the GAINS model produces emission scenarios for the non-CO₂ GHGs and air pollutants, including assessments of future mitigation potentials and marginal abatement cost curves for the non-CO₂ GHGs for each European Union member state. Consistency between GAINS and other models is maintained by GAINS importing macroeconomic, population and energy sector activity drivers from PRIMES, e.g., fuel production and consumption, and agricultural activity data, e.g., livestock numbers and fertilizer use, from the CAPRI agricultural model. Internally in GAINS, activity drivers for other relevant sectors e.g., waste, wastewater, and F-gas use in air conditioning and refrigeration, are generated in consistency with the macroeconomic drivers provided by the PRIMES model. Feedback loops to take account of non-CO₂ mitigation opportunities available through structural changes, e.g., shifts in EU consumer preferences for ruminant products like meat and milk, can be assessed through links established between the GAINS and the CAPRI and GLOBIOM models. Another feedback loop has been established between the GAINS and PRIMES models to ensure consistency in resource efficiency of waste generation and management, in particular with regard to the supply limitations of organic carbon embedded in different waste streams that can be made available as feedstock for renewable energy generation.

2.1.6.3 Modelling air pollution - Atmospheric dispersion

An integrated assessment of air pollution needs to link changes in precursor emissions from the various sources to responses in impact indicators at receptors. Traditionally this task is accomplished by comprehensive atmospheric chemistry and transport models, which simulate a complex range of chemical and physical reactions. The GAINS integrated assessment analysis relies on the Unified EMEP Eulerian model, which describes the fate of emissions in the atmosphere considering more than one hundred chemical reactions involving 70 chemical species with time steps down to 20 seconds, including numerous non-linear mechanisms (Simpson et al., 2003; Fagerli and Aas, 2008). However, the joint analysis with economic and ecological aspects in the GAINS model requires computationally efficient source-receptor relationships. For this purpose, response surfaces of the impact-relevant air quality indicators are described through mathematically simple formulations. Functional relationships have been developed for changes in annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations, deposition of sulphur and nitrogen compounds as well as in long-term levels of ground-level ozone. The (grid- or country-specific) parameters of these relationships have been derived from a sample of several hundred runs of the full EMEP Eulerian model with systematically perturbed emissions of the individual sources. The approach for ozone is being revised owing to increasing importance of non-linear responses, especially in the cities, to changes in precursor emissions (NO_x, VOC, CH₄, CO) reductions, owing to changed atmospheric

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composition in Europe following control programs for several air pollutants while CH₄ concentrations increase – therefore, ozone impact assessment will not be possible within this project.

Source-receptor relationships have been developed for changes in emissions of SO₂, NO_x, NH₃, VOC and PM_{2.5} for 50 countries in Europe, Central Asia, and five sea areas. The current atmospheric transfer coefficients were updated in 2022 with the latest version of the EMEP model. Several aspects have been revised, including improvement of spatial resolution for all pollutants and indicators and the contributions to ambient PM_{2.5} from primary PM, SO₂ and NO_x emissions have been made sector specific so that each key emission sector is represented with its distinct spatial distribution. The ambient PM_{2.5} concentrations are estimated at a 0.1° x 0.1° resolution and deposition of N and S used for ecosystem impacts are calculated at 0.3°x0.2° resolution.

2.1.6.4 Modelling air pollution and air quality impacts

Health impacts from PM

A large body of epidemiological evidence has shown that both short-term and long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} has negative effects on human health and increases mortality from several diseases. GAINS focuses on the effects of long-term exposure and calculates mortality related indicators: the number of premature (attributable) deaths, the shortening of life expectancy, and the number of life years lost. Besides mortality, exposure to PM_{2.5} also causes a high burden of morbidity. Currently this burden is not quantified in GAINS. Development is ongoing to include it in the future.

Attributable mortality (burden) refers to the past and is defined as the reduction in the number of deaths that would have been possible if past population exposure to ambient PM_{2.5} had shifted to an alternative or counterfactual level, keeping other conditions unchanged. These are deaths that likely occurred earlier than would be expected in the absence of air pollution (i.e., premature deaths). In contrast, avoidable mortality (burden) refers to the future and is defined as the potential reduction in future number of deaths that could be achieved by changing the current and future distribution of exposure of ambient PM_{2.5} to a counterfactual distribution of exposure (Murray et al. 2020).

Similar to the Global Burden of Disease project, estimations of excess number of deaths associated with ambient fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) in GAINS are based on a comparative risk assessment (CRA) methodology. Within the CRA, the change in population health outcomes are estimated under alternative scenarios based on a different distribution of exposure to a risk factor over time and using Population Attributable Fractions (PAFs). The risk assessment of the mortality burden from ambient PM_{2.5} requires five key components:

1. baseline ambient PM_{2.5} concentrations – in GAINS these are validated against monitoring data;
2. estimates of the distribution of population exposure to ambient PM_{2.5} – in GAINS these are combined with gridded and total population data for each region to estimate population-weighted exposures;
3. baseline death rates and population size (by cause, age and potentially sex) – these age-specific mortality data in GAINS are derived from the UN World Population Prospects 2017 (UNDESA, 2017);
4. exposure-response functions (ERFs) that cover the entire exposure distribution – from the highest level to the counterfactual level - ERFs use the best available epidemiological evidence to relate different levels of long-term exposure to ambient PM_{2.5} to the increased risk of an adverse health effect. ERFs are normally represented by relative risk (RR) functions, which show the ratio of the probability of death by a certain age given a specific exposure to the probability of death at that age assuming a counterfactual exposure (Burnett et al., 2018). The ERFs used in GAINS have been changing over time

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following the latest WHO or GBD methodology;

5. counterfactual risk exposure level - it is a baseline or reference exposure level, against which the contribution of the risk factor (ambient PM_{2.5}) to the disease burden and the benefits of its removal are estimated. For Europe, the counterfactual ambient PM_{2.5} in GAINS is set to the sum of all natural contributions (dust and sea salt).

Importantly, analysis which aims to quantify future deaths that could be avoided if policy action is taken to reduce exposure also needs to take into account future changes in underlying mortality rates, size, distribution and age structure of the population of interest (Burnett & Cohen, 2020). It has been shown that these demographic factors can have a larger influence on mortality than the projected changes in ambient PM_{2.5} (Rafaj et al., 2021). Different data sources and assumptions regarding the four components of the CRA can generate substantial differences in estimates.

Years of Life lost (YLLs) are a measure for the total loss of human life span in a given country due to the exposure to PM_{2.5} in a given year. They are calculated by multiplying age-specific attributable deaths with the remaining life expectancy at this age and summing over all ages. The remaining life expectancy at a given age and region is taken from a life table; currently GAINS uses UN World Population Prospects 2017 (UN 2017) and these are regularly updated over time as new projections become available.

Ecosystem impacts

The critical loads approach employed by the GAINS model for the quantification of ecosystems risks from acidification and eutrophication uses (ecosystem-specific) annual mean deposition of acidifying compounds (i.e., sulphur, oxidized and reduced nitrogen) as the impact-relevant air quality indicator. Critical load database has been provided by the Coordination Centre for Effects (CCE), based at UBA, Germany; latest version in 2021. Significant non-linearities in the spatial source-receptor relationships due to co-deposition with ammonia have been found for the substantial emission reductions that have occurred over the last two decades (Fowler et al., 2005). However, the EMEP Eulerian model suggests – for the technically feasible range of further emissions reductions beyond the baseline projection – nearly linear responses in annual mean deposition of sulphur and nitrogen compounds towards changes in SO₂, NO_x and NH₃ emissions.

2.1.7 Current model interlinkages

There are already established soft linkages among models involved in the EU consortium modelling toolbox, which have been interconnected for many years (Figure 9). These models have been used since the EU Reference Scenario 2016 and in the EU Reference Scenario 2020. The interlinkage allows the models within the modelling toolbox to run coherently and represent economy-wide GHG emissions coherently.

Figure 9. EU Modeling Suite Linkage

The specific model linkage is described below. The output of the models on the left-hand side will be fed into models on the right-hand side of the arrow.

1. GEM-E3 and PRIMES → all models in the EU modelling toolbox
 - a. Economic projections
 - b. Demographic projections
2. PROMETHEUS to PRIMES → all models in the EU modelling toolbox
 - a. International fuel prices
3. PRIMES → GAINS
 - a. Activity and energy consumption by sector
 - b. The stock of vehicles
 - c. Bioenergy supply and demand
4. PRIMES energy system → PRIMES biomass supply → GLOBIOM/G4M
 - a. PRIMES internally interact for quantity and prices of bio-energy products
 - b. Bio-energy requirements in terms of energy crops and forestry feedstock are passed on to GLOBIOM/G4M
5. GLOBIOM/G4M → PRIMES
 - a. Biomass supply on land and resource (residue and waste feedstocks) availability
 - b. Yield and costs of forestry related products incl. residues
 - c. CO₂ LULUCF marginal abatement cost curves (MACC)

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6. GAINS → PRIMES
 - a. Yield and costs of waste, incl. agricultural residues
 - b. Non-CO₂ marginal abatement cost curves (MACC)
7. GLOBIOM → GAINS/GAINS → GLOBIOM
 - a. Harmonized relating to agricultural mitigation option possibilities

2.2 China consortium modelling toolbox

2.2.1 AGHG-INV

2.2.1.1 Model overview

Agriculture-induced non-CO₂ **GHG IN**ventory (AGHG-INV) is a bottom-up model based on the Tier 2 method of the IPCC 2006 Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories (IPCC, 2006). It is a province-level non-CO₂ greenhouse gas (GHG) emission inventory for China's agricultural sector (Chen et al., 2022). The AGHG-INV model is built upon publicly available activity data from China's national statistical database.⁴ Specifically, it covers CH₄ and N₂O emissions from six agricultural sectors including enteric fermentation, manure management, rice cultivation, agricultural residues burning and freshwater aquaculture. The AGHG-INV model comprehensively estimates and projects China's agricultural non-CO₂ GHG emission pathways from 1980 to 2060 under the business-as-usual scenario (BAU), technical potential scenario (TP), and maximum technical potential scenario (MTP). Innovative aspects of the AGHG-INV model include covering non-CO₂ GHG emissions from freshwater aquaculture, better spatial representation of the emission factors and a detailed inventory of agricultural non-CO₂ GHG mitigation technologies.

Figure 10 illustrates the conceptual framework of the AGHG-INV. It comprises three modules, inventory development, scenario analysis and result interpretation.

2.2.1.1 Modelling non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions in China

Inventory development

Inventories of agricultural non-CO₂ GHG emissions have been developed mainly based on either process models or emission factor approaches. The AGHG-INV model is developed by emission factor approaches, because the method based on emission factors can alleviate the data acquisition problem to a large extent (Ma et al., 2022). This inventory uses provincial activity data and region-specific emission factors, and considers provincial agricultural management (Chen et al., 2022).

The AGHG-INV model calculated enteric fermentation CH₄ emissions from eight types of livestock including beef cattle, dairy cattle, goat, sheep, pig and so on. Manure management is a source of CH₄ and N₂O emissions. When estimating non-CO₂ GHG emissions from manure management, the AGHG-INV model considers thirteen manure management methods for different livestock at the provincial level. For CH₄ emissions from rice cultivation, region-specific emission factors for three rice categories (early rice, middle rice, and late rice) are used. Province-level N₂O emissions from agricultural land are divided into direct emissions and indirect

⁴ <https://data.stats.gov.cn/english/easyquery.htm?cn=Co1>

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emissions. Direct emissions from agricultural land are derived from N fertilizer application, manure application and straw incorporation. Indirect emissions from agricultural land come from N deposition, leaching and runoff. For CH₄ and N₂O emissions from agricultural residue burning, the AGHG-INV model considers province-level straw incorporation of sixteen crops such as rice, wheat and maize. Finally, based on Yuan et al. (2019), the AGHG-INV model estimates CH₄ and N₂O emissions from freshwater aquaculture by distinguishing rice-fish systems, semi-intensive systems, and intensive systems.

Figure 10. The conceptual framework diagram of the AGHG-INV model

Scenario analysis

Based on the differences of demographic changes, economic growth, urbanization process and technology diffusion, three scenarios are developed to explore China’s agricultural non-CO₂ emission pathways.

Business-as-usual scenario (BAU). The demographic changes, economic growth, and urbanization process under the BAU scenario in the AGHG-INV model are followed shared socioeconomic pathways, including SSP1 (sustainability), SSP2 (intermediate pathways), SSP3 (regional competition), SSP4 (inequality), and SSP5 (fossil fuel development). The SSP2 scenario is used as an intermediate storyline for the BAU scenario. In addition, the BAU scenario also assumes that self-sufficiency rate and uses of different foods remain the same compared to 2022 (Tong et al., 2023); the productivity of each food type keeps at the actual level of 2022 (Ma et al., 2019); the spatial layout of food production maintain at the actual level in 2022 (Bai et al., 2018); mitigation measures are not diffused.

Technical potential scenario (TP). The TP scenario evaluates the physical mitigation potential of currently

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available technologies or practices, showing a conventional technology development path. The TP scenario consists of 11 mitigation technologies for the crop farming sector and 6 mitigation technologies for the livestock feeding sector, where each technology considers the mitigation efficiency of multiple non-CO₂ GHGs. Each technology's mitigation potential is determined by its technical applicability, implementation potential and emission reduction efficiency. Despite their great relevance, the technologies or practices that reduced emission intensity only by increasing productivity and structural change were not included in the technology inventory.

Maximum technical potential scenario (MTP). The MTP scenario evaluates the upper limit of physical mitigation for China's agricultural sector without considering technical, economic, or social implementation barriers across regions. The basic calculation process for the MTP scenario is the same as that of the TP scenario. However, the MTP scenario assumes the complete application of all available mitigation technologies by 2060.

Projection of activity data. The AGHG-INV model projects activity data based on the projection of food demand per capita. Food demand per capita is calculated based on the relationships between demand per capita for food calories and a series of indexes such as GDP per capita and urbanization rate. Based on the assumptions about the self-sufficiency rate, productivity, share for human consumption, and spatial layout of food production, province-level agricultural activity data can be projected.

2.2.2 GTAP

2.2.2.1 Model overview

The GTAP (Global Trade Analysis Project) is a publicly funded project based in academia at Purdue University⁵. It is a multi-regional, multi-sector computable general equilibrium model used for analyzing international trade policies, economic integration, and global economic issues. Based on a comprehensive global economic database, the model is widely applied in trade policy assessment, regional economic studies, and environmental policy analysis.

The standard GTAP Model is a multiregion, multisector, computable general equilibrium model, with perfect competition and constant returns to scale. Innovative aspects of this model include:

1. The treatment of private household preferences using the non-homothetic CDE functional form.
2. The explicit treatment of international trade and transport margins. Bilateral trade is handled via the Armington assumption.
3. A global banking sector which intermediates between global savings and consumption.

The GTAP Model also gives users a wide range of closure options, including unemployment, tax revenue replacement and fixed trade balance closures, and a selection of partial equilibrium closures (which facilitate comparison of results to studies based on partial equilibrium assumptions).

2.2.2.2 Environmental and Energy Research

Many economic analyses of climate policies have used computable general equilibrium (CGE) models of the global economy. This class of model permits the analysis of policy impacts while considering all the

⁵ www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu

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substitutions and exchanges that occur in the global economy. The GTAP Model and data base at Purdue has been used extensively to evaluate costs of abatement and to assess the spill-over effects of greenhouse gases (GHG) abatement policies via international trade and sectoral interaction. During the past decade, the Global Trade Analysis Project has filled an important need in the integrated assessment (IA) community by providing regular updates of world-wide input-output and bilateral trade data sets with significant disaggregation of regions and sectors, plus energy volume data. GTAP has successfully integrated global energy data sets - in particular, extended energy balances and energy prices and taxes, compiled by the International Energy Agency (IEA) - into the GTAP input-output tables and bilateral trade data (first implementation). With its data base now covering inputs/outputs and bilateral trade of 57 commodities (and producing industries) and 113 countries/regions, GTAP is able to capture broad sectoral interactions within domestic economies and international trade effects as well.

Recently, growing research demands for integrated assessment (IA) of climate change issues and bio-fuels have motivated construction of data bases and models related to GHG emissions, Land use, and Biofuels which can be used with CGE models.

GHG Emissions

Based on the GTAP energy volume data, we further estimated the CO₂ emissions by fuel and by user for each country/region. This gives more accurate estimates of CO₂ emission coefficients, which is essential in the derivation of marginal abatement costs - one of the key factors in the global market of emissions trading. In addition to the GTAP energy data sets, the GTAP-E model has been developed to better describe the behavior of energy consumers in the face of higher energy prices. For example, taxes on CO₂ emissions would prompt energy consumers to use less-polluting energy, such as natural gas as opposed to coal. In addition, GTAP-E also allows for analyses of the "carbon leakage" effect and global emissions trading.

With funding from EPA, we are currently extending the GTAP Data Base further to include non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions - CH₄, N₂O, and F-gases. Emissions of these gases are linked to the underlying economic drivers of emissions - mostly agriculture. In this EPA project, we also aim to further extend the GTAP Data Base to allow it to support analyses of the linkages between land use changes and net GHG emissions from agriculture and forestry. We develop a new GTAP-based model - named GTAPE-AEZ - to illustrate how the GHG emissions from agricultural and forestry activities could be integrated into the standard GTAP Model or other similar CGE models.

Land Use

Growing research demands for integrated assessment of GHGs issues also motivated construction of a Data Base of land use and GHG emissions for use with CGE models. This project, funded by the Methane and Sequestration Branch of the US Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), aims to further extend the GTAP Data Base to fill the gap that links land use changes and GHGs emissions from agriculture and forestry. The extended GTAP Data Base covers major GHGs from all sources, with a special focus on GHG emissions related to changes in land use and management practices in agriculture and forestry (e.g., deforestation and afforestation). The EPA sponsored project also identifies a methodological approach to integrate GHGs emissions from agricultural and forestry activities into the standard GTAP Model. Cost features of alternative GHG abatement technologies are also incorporated into the model.

Bio-fuels

Most recently the GTAP Model and data base have been extended to improve the treatment of biofuel by products and accurately represent global land use. The modified model, nick-named GTAP-BIO (Birur et al.,

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2008) further modifies the GTAP-E model (Burniaux and Truong, 2002 and modified by McDougall and Golub, 2009) to incorporate the potential for biofuels to substitute for petroleum products. Biofuels were also introduced into this GTAP Data Base (Taheripour et al., 2007). The modified data base includes data on production, consumption and trade of biofuels including grain based ethanol, sugarcane ethanol, and biodiesel from oilseeds, as well as data on biofuel by-products.

2.2.2.3 Land Use and Land Cover

The GTAP 9 Land Use and Land Cover Data Base builds global land cover and land use databases for base years: 2004, 2007 and 2011. Unlike previous versions, the data is directly constructed from publicly available geospatial maps (circa 2000/01 at 5-minute grid resolution). These are then aggregated for each AEZ-region and updated to each base year using national level output price, land use and land cover information from FAOSTAT (2016).

Crop land use and land cover, pasture land cover as well as potential vegetation maps are based on the 5-minute grid resolution of the geospatial information used in constructing the original GTAP 6 LULC. This consists of agricultural land cover from Ramankutty et al (2008), land use data for 172 crops from Monfreda et al (2008) and potential vegetation from Ramankutty and Foley (1999) which are all available for download at www.Earthstat.org.

2.2.2.4 CGE Baseline

Thomas Chappuis joined the Center for Global Trade Analysis to assist with the development of a new baseline for the Dynamic GTAP Model and to set up this baseline page where GTAP users can easily find and contribute data sources, baseline documentation and programs.

Chappuis, Thomas, and Terrie Walmsley, while constructing a new baseline for the GDyn model, spent considerable time collecting projections and deciding on the appropriate data to use. They developed programs to aggregate projections for any specific geographical aggregation of the GTAP Data Base. To assist researchers in building their own baselines, they created a section on the GTAP website where users can access projections data and aggregation programs. The purpose of their work is to document the data used in the new GDyn baseline and provide a user guide for the baseline website, with the view that sharing data and expertise will aid in creating reliable and defensible baseline scenarios. Similarly, Walmsley, Betina Dimaranan, and Robert McDougall developed a base case scenario for the Dynamic GTAP Model, responding to the growing interest in dynamic models, particularly the Dynamic GTAP model at the Center for Global Trade Analysis. Their paper demonstrates how such a scenario, depicting potential changes in the world economy over the next 20 years, was created. The base case scenario was constructed using a program at the Center for Global Trade Analysis, which allows users to input macro and policy forecasts, alter policy implementation assumptions, and aggregate over time, regions, and commodities. Although designed for the Dynamic GTAP model, the program is general enough to be used with other models, though it primarily focuses on standard macro aggregates without offering alternative scenarios.

2.2.2.5 Labor Migration

The economics literature increasingly recognizes the importance of migration and its ties with many other aspects of development and policy. In 2003, Walmsley and Winters demonstrated utilizing a Global Migration model (GMig) that lifting restrictions on the movement of natural persons would significantly increase global welfare with the majority of benefits accruing to developing countries. Although an important result, the lack of bilateral labor migration data forced Walmsley and Winters to make approximations in important areas and

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naturally precluded their tracking bilateral migration agreements. Since then the model has been extended to incorporate bilateral migration flows and dynamics.

In 2005, the Center for Global Trade Analysis, in collaboration with the Development Research Centre on Migration, Globalisation and Poverty, Sussex University, United Kingdom, the Department for International Development, United Kingdom and the World Bank, Washington D.C., USA, have developed a data base for use in analysis of Labor migration issues. The result of this collaboration has been a bilateral matrix of the home and host regions of the World's 176.6 million international migrants and the development of the GMig2 model and Data Base. The data was used by the World Bank in their production of the 2006 Global Economic Prospects and has appeared in the Guardian and on Vox.

More recently (2010) in collaboration with the World Bank, one thousand census and population register records were combined to construct decennial matrices corresponding to the last five completed census rounds (available at <http://data.worldbank.org/data-catalog/global-bilateral-migration-database>).

2.2.2.6 Poverty and Trade Liberalization

The book "Poverty and the WTO: Impacts of the Doha Development Agenda", edited by Thomas W. Hertel and L. Alan Winters, a co-publication of the World Bank and Palgrave Macmillan (available immediately, with a 2006 publication date), reports on the findings from a major international research project investigating the poverty impacts of a potential Doha Development Agenda. It combines in a novel way the results from several strands of research. Firstly, it draws on an intensive analysis of the DDA Framework Agreement, with particularly close attention paid to potential reforms in agriculture. The scenarios are built up using newly available tariff line data and their implications for world markets are established using the GTAP global modeling framework. These world trade impacts, in turn, form the basis for thirteen country case studies of the national poverty impacts of these DDA scenarios. The focus countries include: Bangladesh, Brazil (2 studies), Cameroon, China (2 studies), Indonesia, Mexico, Mozambique, Philippines, Russia, Vietnam and Zambia. While the diversity of approaches taken in these studies limits the ability to draw broader conclusions, an additional study which provides a 15 country cross-section analysis is aimed at this objective. Finally, a global analysis provides estimates for the world as a whole.

2.2.3 Current model interlinkages

It is important to note that there is no direct linkage between the GTAP model and the AGHG-INV model. GTAP is a global computable general equilibrium model that relies on data from multiple countries across various dimensions such as economic activity, social factors, greenhouse gas emissions, and land use to simulate the impacts of international trade and policy on national economies and the environment. In contrast, AGHG-INV focuses solely on the estimation and projection of province-level agricultural non-CO₂ GHG emissions in China. As such, these two models are independent of one another in terms of geographic scope, data requirements, and objectives.

3 Current model limitations and potential improvements

This section explores the current limitations of each model. These discussions will explain the challenges and constraints faced by the models in their current state of art, including shortcomings in their methodology, data, or application scope. Following the identification of these limitations, a list of potential improvements for each model is present. These recommendations aim to enhance the models' accuracy, reliability, and overall effectiveness in applications to the project.

3.1 EU consortium modelling toolbox

3.1.1 GEM-E3

In the context of the project, GEM-E3 model could be further developed in the following ways:

3.1.1.1 Improved representation of the transformational challenges of key carbon-intensive industrial sectors

The specific model developments to be delivered aim to capture i) the availability of capital fundings for new investment towards the decarbonization of the production process, ii) understanding the labour market challenges in terms of new/different skills requirements on the path to decarbonising these industries, and iii) a more granular understanding of these value chains. The sectors of primary focus are petrochemicals, steel and cement production.

3.1.1.2 Improved representation of circular economy

The GEM-E3-CIRC module will be further refined to include the more up-to-date estimation of an Environmental and Material Input-Output table, and will further include circular economy measures as further mitigation options. This will also allow to understand the synergies between mitigation and circular economy, as well as the economic potential of circular economy practices. The focus will be in further identifying the potential of secondary material use and the cost implications with a focus on steel production.

3.1.1.3 Improved representation of critical value chains relevant to the transition

The scope is to enhance the modeling capacity to capture potential economic opportunities and challenges arising from the climate and energy transition. It focuses on identifying and understanding the emergence of novel industrial and services sectors, as well as value chains, resulting from this transition. A focus will be to improve the representation of the value chain of specific clean technology sectors such as electric vehicles, batteries, PV modules, Wind turbines and to quantify the investments and value generation associated with the emergence of new technologies such as hydrogen and carbon capture.

3.1.1.4 Improved representation of low-carbon energy carriers

The representation of new, low-carbon energy carriers will be improved in the model, with a focus on hydrogen and advanced biofuels, by incorporating in a sophisticated manner the use of these fuels to the different end users, including industry and transportation. Particular consideration will be put on capturing cost implications and labor and capital requirements for the sectors and the economy.

3.1.1.5 Enhancement of the model reporting

The model reporting routines will be enhanced to incorporate all necessary variables required for the project.

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This includes identifying and integrating additional variables that reflect key aspects of the climate policy frameworks, economic sectors, and emissions data relevant to the project's focus areas. These improvements will ensure comprehensive coverage of the data needed for accurate modeling and analysis, with clear definitions and consistency across all components of the model, using and further improving the IPCC/IAMC data template.

3.1.2 PRIMES

In the context of the project, the PRIMES model could be enhanced in the following areas:

3.1.2.1 Better calibration to more recent data and update of technology assumptions

The PRIMES model is currently being updated to include the latest year as a statistical year and use it as a basis for model calibration. The model calibration process is essential to ensure that the modelling tool can accurately reproduce a given observed year. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the years 2020 and subsequent years have particularities, as consumer behaviour and industrial activity have been significantly affected. As the economy gradually recovered from the effects of COVID-19, updating the model with the more recent dataset is very helpful to represent reality better. A second part of this task involves updating techno-economic assumptions used as input in the modelling. Due to the fast-changing landscape in energy and climate, developments in new low-carbon technologies have occurred recently. Especially, for technologies that are not yet mature but are necessary to achieve climate neutrality, such as synthetic methane production, electrolysis, and DAC, updating the technology assumptions according to more recent data is of utmost importance.

3.1.2.2 Enhancement of representation of CO₂ capture, storage and use modelling

The supply chain of CO₂ and the representation of carbon as a feedstock is an increasingly important feature that modelling tools should include, especially when analysing decarbonisation scenarios. The PRIMES model already includes the modelling of CC(U)S, but this will be further enhanced so as to capture in more detail the interaction between the different sources (DAC, CCS, biogenic) and origins of CO₂ (synthetic hydrocarbons, storage in materials, underground storage). This includes enhancing modelling process-related emissions to reflect better the different options for abating carbon dioxide emissions by increasing the technology and sector segmentation.

3.1.2.3 Enhancement of representation of low-carbon fuels

Sector coupling and system integration are important features of the green transition strategies that the modelling already simulates. However, an enhancement of this is planned for the following period. The production of green hydrogen optimally integrates with the power system's hourly patterns, which transform to absorb large amounts of stochastic renewable resources. The electrolysis operating with adequate hourly patterns smooths the power load net of renewables and, thus, acts as a virtual power storage. Facilities for storing gas and synthetic methane contribute as a virtual (long-term) seasonal storage of electricity, as green hydrogen production for synthetic methane takes place mainly at times of renewable resource abundance. Also, cross-border trade simulated in PRIMES is expanded to handle hydrogen and synthetic fuels (prospectively also carbon dioxide), enhancing system flexibility and optimising integration with the power system and renewables. Sector coupling also concerns carbon dioxide capture and re-use, such as capturing from process emissions and re-using in synthetic methane production.

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3.1.2.4 Enhancement of representation of the aviation and maritime modules

These enhancements are planned so as to capture in a more detailed way how policies that target emission reduction in these transport segments impact the sectors. The aviation model will be enhanced so as to include other technologies, such as hydrogen aircrafts and also distinguish the flights between low-cost and full-service ones. For the maritime module, the enhancement concerns the split of waterborne transport between inland waterways and domestic maritime. Additionally, the model will be enhanced so as to better reflect operational efficiency improvements of the vessels' fleet and new technologies (e.g., ammonia, methanol).

3.1.3 PROMETHEUS

In the context of the project, the PROMETHEUS model could be enhanced in the following ways:

3.1.3.1 Better calibration to more recent data

The calibration of the model is a critical step that ensures the model's parameters and outputs align with real-world data and observations. The model will be fully calibrated up to 2022/2023 and where possible to even more recent data, specifically for energy system variables (energy demand, supply, prices) and associated CO₂ emissions. The base year will be set to a recent year, preferably 2022 (post COVID-era) enabling the same trajectory for all scenarios for the past period.

3.1.3.2 Enhanced modeling of industrial processes and technologies

PROMETHEUS has a detailed representation of industrial processes and sectors. This representation will be enhanced based on recent data, especially for energy intensive industries such as iron and steel, chemicals and cement sectors. Emphasis will be given on the improvement of the representation of low-carbon technological options, including novel options like deep electrification by industrial sector, direct hydrogen use for steel-making, carbon capture and storage, use of clean synthetic e-fuels, and circular economy strategies.

3.1.3.3 Improvement of the representation of low-carbon fuels

Hydrogen, e-fuels and advanced biofuels are required for the energy transition especially in sectors with limited potential for electrification (e.g., heavy industry, aviation, shipping). The model will be further enhanced to represent the use of these fuels in various demand sectors with a focus on transport and specific industrial processes, such as the production of steel and chemicals. Specifically in the transportation sector, representation will be improved for low- and zero-carbon technologies for all transport modes, including international shipping and aviation. The model will also include various technological pathways for the production of hydrogen, e-fuels and advanced biofuels using recent techno-economic data from the IEA and the EC Reference scenario 2020.

3.1.3.4 Technological, financial and regional improvements

Assumptions regarding the technology cost development and the capital investment cost of low- and zero-carbon technologies required for decarbonization will be improved based on the most recent developments and available data (IEA and EC Reference Scenario 2020). The capital Cost of capital will be differentiated by region and technology in the electricity sector and the technological learning formulation will be updated to the latest estimates of learning rates, with focus on clean energy technologies (including renewable energy technologies for power production, electric vehicle, heat pumps, fuel cells, electrolyzers). Furthermore, RES potentials by region will be updated based on the latest projections and estimations of demand for energy services will be revised to follow the latest socio-economic developments by region and sector.

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3.1.3.5 Improvement of the representation of climate policy instruments

This process involves the refinement of the representation of energy and climate policies in the PROMETHEUS model such as carbon pricing, emissions trading, renewable energy incentives, and regulations (e.g., CO₂ emissions standards, phase-out of polluting technologies etc.). This enhancement ensures that PROMETHEUS will more accurately reflect the impacts of climate and energy policies and provide more robust insights into the effectiveness of various strategies for achieving emission reduction targets and transitioning toward a low-carbon economy in major economies globally. Special attention will be given to the policies in the EU and China, as these regions are the primary focus of the project. This ensures a detailed and accurate representation of their unique climate strategies and regulatory frameworks within the model.

3.1.3.6 Enhancement of the model reporting

The model reporting routines will be enhanced to incorporate all necessary variables required for the project. This includes identifying and integrating additional variables that reflect key aspects of the climate policy frameworks, economic sectors, and emissions data relevant to the project's focus areas. These improvements will ensure comprehensive coverage of the data needed for accurate modeling and analysis, with clear definitions and consistency across all components of the model, using and further improving the IPCC/IAMC data template.

3.1.4 GLOBIOM/G₄M

Many GHG mitigation options have been implemented in the GLOBIOM/G₄M model. However, a few innovative land-based mitigation technologies have not yet been incorporated into the EU version of the GLOBIOM and G₄M model suite in great detail. Including a more detailed representation of mitigation technologies at the EU country level will provide new insights into the decarbonization pathways for each member state. Therefore, improving and refining the application of these mitigation technologies at a higher spatial resolution is essential for assessing the mitigation potential within the LULUCF sector in GLOBIOM-EU/G₄M. Potential improvements for the GLOBIOM/G₄M are as follows.

3.1.4.1 Improvements of restoration cost for drained organic soils

Wetlands serve as significant carbon sinks for climate change mitigation in the EU but have experienced rapid loss since 1970 (Wetlands International, 2023). Drained peatlands, a subset of wetlands, contribute approximately 5% to the EU's total greenhouse gas emissions (European Commission, 2021). Rewetting and restoring these peatlands is one of the most effective nature-based solutions for climate mitigation, adaptation, and other environmental benefits. This land-based mitigation strategy is a key part of the AR6 and the EU's 2030 soil strategy, aiming to restore the water table and vegetation cover to promote peat formation. Economically, rewetting involves factors such as land rental prices, lost agricultural profits, and compensation. Currently, GLOBIOM-EU incorporates peatland rewetting with simplified cost assumptions, but more detailed data and model structures on restoration costs is required to better understand the trade-offs and synergies linked to wetland restoration.

3.1.4.2 Implementation of Biochar as a mitigation technology in GLOBIOM-EU

Biochar is the natural decomposition of residual biomass such as forest residues, agriculture residues, and organic waste that releases large amounts of carbon into the atmosphere. Biochar is a technology which allows the conversion of residual biomass in a stable undecomposable format where carbon can be stored for centuries (Zhang, et al., 2022). Biochar's climate-change mitigation potential stems primarily from its slower

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decomposition rate from the raw biomass from which it is generated. This lowers the rate at which photosynthetically fixed C is returned to the atmosphere (Woolf, et al., 2018), and it is considered a negative emission technology (NET) by the IPCC (Lehmann, et al., 2021). Biochar is not currently available in GLOBIOM-EU as a mitigation technology, and the implementation of biochar might result in trade-offs on the use of biomass, which would have significant impacts on the demand in the market.

3.1.4.3 Improvements of agroforestry on pasture land

Agroforestry is broadly defined as "land use systems in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land" (Article 23 of Regulation 1305/2013). These systems have been part of traditional farming practices in many European landscapes, including hedgerows, wood pasture, orchard grazing, and forest grazing. Agroforestry can be divided into two main types: silvoarable systems, where crops and trees are grown together on the same land, and silvopastoral systems, where grassland for livestock is integrated with a significant number of trees. Silvopastoral agroforestry systems are highly effective in offering significant climate mitigation benefits while enhancing crop yields, which improves the capacity to adapt to climate change. While silvopastoral agroforestry systems have been included into the GLOBIOM-EU model, they are mainly driven by exogenous assumptions on their expansion rate. Furthermore, synergies between grass productivity and tree growth have not been accounted for, resulting in a conservative definition of this important mitigation opportunity. To accurately assess the mitigation potential of these systems, a refinement of input data, including information on area, costs, and yields, are essential. Furthermore, efficiency gains between grass and tree production shall be explored, based on scientific literature studies.

3.1.4.4 Improvement of deadwood representation in G4M

Increasing intensity of natural disturbances in forests highlights the importance of modeling the deadwood pool dynamics and management activities such as salvage logging. In the current version of G4M, wood damaged by disturbances is salvaged in one year and the forest is assumed to be regenerated immediately. In reality, the capacity of salvage logging is limited, and it may take a few years to clean and regenerate the damaged forest. For initializing the deadwood pool we use a map by Derci Augustynczyk et al. (2024), however, the map is not fully consistent with the forest management activities as carried out in G4M. The inconsistency of the initial value of the deadwood pool, and the deadwood input and output flows distort the estimation of deadwood emissions. To address this point, the deadwood pool could be disaggregated into one pool representing damaged wood that can be salvaged and another pool representing deadwood that stays in the forest and decomposes over time. This disaggregation will allow use of available information on deadwood pool size and salvage logging more effectively. Introduction of calibration of the initial value of the deadwood pool through a spin-up run of the model with historical average inputs and outputs for the deadwood pool. The calibration is necessary to correct the inconsistency in input data and bring the deadwood pool in equilibrium with the forest state and forest management during the historical period.

3.1.5 GAINS

3.1.5.1 Generation of non-CO₂ emissions and mitigation scenarios and air pollution impact assessments consistent with extended PRIMES energy sector pathways

Apply the extended PRIMES to GAINS link described in 3.1.5.1 to generate consistent non-CO₂ emissions and mitigation scenarios and air pollution impact assessments. The extension will require adaptations of existing data exchange templates between the PRIMES and GAINS models and extended sector and technology structures in GAINS to accommodate new sectors and fuel combinations relevant for the new regions covered

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in PRIMES.

3.1.6 Model interlinkages within EU consortium

3.1.6.1 Adapting GAINS data import link to extended regional scope of the PRIMES model

The existing model link from PRIMES to GAINS concerns the transfer of energy and transport sector activity drivers, as well as macroeconomic and population projections, for the 27 European Union member states, the United Kingdom, and nine countries in Eastern Europe (Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Georgia, Kosovo, North Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Serbia, Ukraine). The PRIMES activity drivers are imported into GAINS and further disaggregated to sectors and technology structures relevant for assessments of air pollution and non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions. With the regional scope of the PRIMES model being extended to other major world regions, the data mapping tables and import format to GAINS must be adapted to appropriately represent emission and mitigation potential estimations in GAINS relevant for the extended PRIMES regions.

3.2 China consortium modelling toolbox

3.2.1 AGHG-INV

3.2.1.1 Improvement of emission factors with finer spatial and temporal resolutions

There are still several constraints that might impede the accuracy and applicability of the AGHG-INV model. Foremost among these is constant and relatively coarse emission factors. For example, CH₄ emission factors of enteric fermentation and manure management are confirmed to have a significant temporal trend (Wang et al., 2024). In addition, emission factors of rice cultivation and agricultural land are at the regional level rather than the provincial level. Thus, it will be important to develop a database and methodological framework to identify emission factors with a consideration of complex impacts of climate, environment, land, agricultural practices, and technology adoption.

3.2.1.2 Improvement of key coefficients for scenarios

Constant self-sufficiency rates of different foods present another limitation. According to Huang et al. (2022), self-sufficiency rates of beef, milk and mutton in China are projected to reduce by 31%, 15% and 28%, respectively from 2019 to 2050. Although the assumption about constant self-sufficiency rates considers food security, it might overestimate China's agricultural non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions. Another limitation is that the model did not fully consider the change in spatial layout of food production. For example, the share of beef cattle in Henan to the national number was reduced from 11% in 2000 to 4% in 2022; the share of the goat in Shandong to the national number was reduced from 11% in 2015 to 4% in 2022. Neglecting the adjustment of provincial agricultural structures reduces the accuracy of provincial emission pathways.

3.2.2 GTAP

Limitations

The Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) model, while widely utilized in economic analyses, exhibits several constraints that merit consideration. Foremost among these is its relatively coarse sectoral disaggregation, comprising 65 sectors, which may inadequately capture the intricacies of contemporary economic structures, particularly in rapidly evolving industries. This limitation is compounded by the model's restricted temporal coverage, with reference years at irregular intervals (2004, 2007, 2011, 2014, and 2017), potentially impeding

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the analysis of recent economic trends and near-term projections.

A significant impediment to the model's applicability in real-time policy analysis is the substantial lag between the reference year and the database release. This temporal discrepancy can diminish the relevance of the model's outputs for addressing contemporary economic challenges. Furthermore, the model's reliance on homogeneity assumptions within sectors and regions may oversimplify the diverse production methods and technologies that characterize modern economies.

The comparative static nature of the GTAP model presents another limitation, as it constrains the model's capacity to capture dynamic effects and adjustment processes over time. This static approach may not adequately represent the complex, evolving nature of global economic systems. Additionally, while GTAP incorporates environmental extensions, these are not as comprehensive as those found in specialized environmental input-output databases, potentially limiting its utility in sustainability analyses.

Lastly, the model's treatment of international trade, based on the Armington assumption, has been subject to criticism for its limitations in accurately representing the complexities of global value chains, which have become increasingly intricate in the modern era of globalization.

Potential improvements

Implementation would require interdisciplinary collaboration and significant research efforts to develop more nuanced algorithms, integrate diverse data sources, and refine econometric techniques, ultimately producing a more comprehensive and responsive economic modeling framework.

3.2.2.1 Improvements of higher sector granularity

The limited sectoral granularity in the current GTAP model presents a significant challenge for accurately capturing the complexities of modern economies, particularly in service-oriented and technology-intensive industries. This lack of detailed sectoral disaggregation can obscure critical economic interactions and interdependencies, leading to oversimplified results. In particular, key sectors that are rapidly evolving or highly specialized may be inadequately represented, reducing the model's ability to provide precise policy insights or predict the full impact of economic shocks and structural changes. Consequently, this limitation impairs both the robustness and relevance of economic analyses derived from the GTAP framework. One key area for improvement is expanding the sectoral resolution of the GTAP model. Increasing the level of disaggregation, particularly in service-oriented sectors like finance, ICT, and professional services, as well as in technology-intensive industries such as renewable energy, pharmaceuticals, and high-tech manufacturing, would enable more detailed analysis. This finer classification would allow for a more accurate representation of industry-specific economic interactions and supply chain interdependencies, offering deeper insights into how these sectors contribute to and shape broader economic trends.

3.2.2.2 Improvements of shorter time intervals

The infrequent updates of the GTAP database present a significant barrier to accurately analyzing recent economic trends and policy impacts. The lag between reference years prevents the model from capturing real-time changes in the global economy, particularly during periods of rapid fluctuations or crises. Moreover, the reliance on annual time steps in dynamic GTAP models limits the model's capacity to detect short-term economic shocks and swift policy responses. To address these issues, increasing the frequency of database updates could substantially reduce the delay between reference years, enhancing the model's relevance for contemporary policy analysis. This would require the adoption of more efficient data collection and processing methods to ensure that updates are timely and accurate. Additionally, improving the dynamic modeling

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framework by incorporating shorter time intervals, such as quarterly or monthly iterations, would enable the model to capture rapid economic fluctuations and policy impacts more effectively, providing a more responsive and detailed tool for economic analysis.

3.2.2.3 Implementation of more comprehensive environmental data

The lack of comprehensive integration between economic activities and their environmental impacts restricts the model's ability to assess critical issues such as resource depletion, pollution, and climate change. Without detailed and harmonized environmental data, GTAP's capacity to model the interdependencies between economic and environmental systems remains inadequate, particularly in sectors like energy and agriculture, where the environmental footprint is substantial. Expanding and refining the environmental extensions within GTAP could augment its utility for sustainability analyses. This improvement would involve the integration of more comprehensive environmental data and the development of methodologies to more effectively link economic activities with their environmental impacts. Improving the integration of GTAP with other specialized databases, such as those focused on energy, agriculture, or environmental factors, could significantly enhance its analytical capabilities. This integration would necessitate the development of robust methodologies for data harmonization and linkage, potentially yielding a more comprehensive and versatile modeling framework.

3.2.2.4 Improvement of firm-level heterogeneity

The current model, which employs aggregate sector-level data, overlooks the substantial variations in firm characteristics, behaviors, and responses to policy changes and external shocks. This lack of detailed microdata prevents the model from capturing the diverse ways in which individual firms—ranging from small enterprises to large corporations—react to economic policies, market conditions, and disruptions. As a result, the GTAP model's analyses may fail to reflect the true complexity of economic systems, leading to less accurate predictions and policy recommendations. Incorporating firm-level heterogeneity through the integration of detailed microdata could substantially enhance the model's realism and precision, providing a more nuanced understanding of economic dynamics and improving the efficacy of policy analyses. The incorporation of firm-level heterogeneity into the GTAP model could provide a more realistic representation of economic structures. This improvement would require the integration of microdata on firm characteristics and behavior, potentially enhancing the model's ability to capture the diverse responses of economic agents to policy changes and external shocks.

3.3 Potential model interlinkages between EU and Chinese models

3.3.1.1 Links between AGHG-INV, GLOBIOM and G4M by coordinating inputs and scenarios

The AGHG-INV model may establish linkages with GLOBIOM in aspects of the projection of food demand, international trade of commodities, emission accounting, and estimation of mitigation potential. Due to focus on the agriculture sector, the connection between the AGHG-INV model and the G4M model is relatively weak.

Data of agricultural activity are derived from National Bureau of Statistics in the AGHG-INV model, while they are from FAOSTAT in the GLOBIOM. Making the data sources of agricultural activity consistent is beneficial for the robustness of the test results. The sources of emission factors also vary. For example, the emission factors of rice cultivation, synthetic fertilizer, and livestock feeding in the GLOBIOM are sourced from FAO, IPCC and Herrero et al. (2013), while those in the AGHG-INV model are derived from the average value of studies based on China.

The GLOBIOM model can provide more accurate data on food demand, production and trade for the AGHG-

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INV model. Compared to the AGHG-INV model, the GLOBIOM additionally considers price factors and the demand for biomass energy when projecting food demand. The BAU scenarios in the AGHG-INV model and GLOBIOM are both followed by the SSP2 scenario. In the future, it may be possible to align the sources of socio-economic data under the SSP2 scenario. This could potentially be done by implementing a soft linkage between the models where GLOBIOM provide the AGHG-INV model with projections of food demand for China, production quantities and intentional trade.

Finally, the mitigation techniques for the two models are very similar under the technical mitigation scenarios. However, the GLOBIOM additionally considers some productivity improvement technologies such as feed supplements and improved cropping compared to the AGHG-INV model. Aligning the technology inventory facilitates the comparison of agricultural mitigation potentials.

3.3.1.1 Bottom-up technology analysis for agricultural sector in collaboration with GAINS

It is possible to enhance the collaboration between the AGHG-INV model and the GAINS model. Currently, AGHG-INV only conducts assessment on technical potentials, However, it does not include an assessment of the costs associated with these technologies. The GAINS model has cost data for non-CO₂ greenhouse gasses and can give the marginal abatement cost curves for non-CO₂ greenhouse gasses in the agricultural sector. The incorporation of mitigation cost curves from GAINS can enhance the economic analysis of the model.

On the other hand, the AGHG-INV model could provide better technical information on the technical applicability, implementation potential, and emission reduction efficiency of agricultural mitigation technologies in China. AGHG-INV can provide that information to GAINS as well. At the same time, the two teams can work together on how to improve the collections of techno-economic information of key technologies, including the criterion for mitigation technology screening, key techno-economic coefficients for potential assessments, and survey strategies.

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